

INFLUENCE OF PROCESS PARAMETERS ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF RTM MOLDINGS

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ABSTRACT

The influence of process parameters on the mechanical behavior of Resin Transfer Molded (RTM) carbon fiber/epoxy laminates was studied experimentally. The parameters studied were injection pressure, vacuum (suction) pressure, mold temperature, and cure regime (temperature and time). Each parameter was varied between two levels, selected according to aerospace manufacturers' requirements. Mechanical performance including tension strength, notched tension and compression strength, and interlaminar delamination toughness in both mode I and mode II were investigated. Comparative tests were performed at room temperature, and elevated temperature and humidity. A total of 640 specimens were tested.

INTRODUCTION

To use the RTM manufacturing technique for e.g. aerospace structures is an interesting alternative to e.g. pre-preg manufacturing. Complex structures with integrated foam cores can be molded in one stage. Manufacturing parameters have to be matched to the specific component manufactured. Bounds on the process parameters are often due to requirements on mold filling time and mold size (large molds require low pressures to avoid large deflections). Further, during mass production process parameters will naturally vary. It is therefore important to know how these process parameter variations affect the mechanical behavior of the finished product. As part of the Brite-Euram project "Simulation of the Resin Transfer Molding Process for Efficient Design and Manufacture of Composite Components" (SimRTM), this investigation of the correlation between process parameters and the composites mechanical behavior was performed. Parameters used as variables were injection pressure, vacuum pressure, mold temperature, and cure regime. A number of rectangular flat plates were molded with different process parameters. The test series was designed to investigate some of the fundamental mechanical properties, including tensile strength of notched and un-notched specimens, Young's modulus, and compression notched failure strength. The influence of environmental conditions – dry and hot/wet, respectively – was investigated for these properties. Interlaminar fracture toughness was measured on dry specimens.

MATERIALS, LAMINATES AND PROCESS CONDITIONS

A total of 32 quadratic, 600x600 mm, carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates were RTM molded using peripheral injection with an evacuation port in the laminate center. All laminates were manufactured by Brochier SA. Two different epoxy resins were used, here referred to as resin A and resin B. The fiber type, weave and layup were kept constant throughout the investigation. 10 layers of 5H satin E3833/EPF weave with Tenax HTA 5131 200 tex F3000 fibers were stacked together and pre-formed. The layup was symmetric with the warp in the same direction in all layers. The nominal laminate thickness for the resin A laminates was 3.0 mm and for the resin B laminates 3.2 mm. However due to mold deformation during injection the laminates were thinner in the center of the plates, see Fig. 1. For the resin A laminates the local fiber volume fraction (v_f) therefore varied between 54.1 % and 61.9 %, and for the resin B laminates between 50.7 % and

58.1 %. This lead to some problems in the interpretation of the results since strength and stiffness are closely related to the fiber amount. A thick specimen did not contain more fibers than a thin specimen and would thus have lower ultimate *stress* and stiffness even if the ultimate *force* of the thick and thin specimens were the same. The moduli and ultimate stresses may therefore be somewhat misleading.

For simplicity all laminates were numbered. Table 1 shows the numbering and the corresponding process parameters. For each combination of process parameters two laminates were fabricated, one of which (laminates with even numbers) contained a 15 μm Teflon crack starter film for the fracture toughness tests. Table 2 shows the values of each process parameter. For convenience in the following the different laminates will be referred to by their numbers rather than their associated full set of RTM process parameters. Laminates nos. 1 to 16 have the resin A matrix and nos. 17 to 32 the resin B matrix.

Table 1. Numbering of the laminates, and associated process parameters.

Resin A laminates				Resin B laminates			
Laminate number	Vacuum pressure	Mold temp	Cure regime	Laminate number	Injection pressure	Mold temp.	Cure regime
1 & 2	High	High	High	17 & 18	High	High	High
3 & 4	High	High	Low	19 & 20	High	High	Low
5 & 6	High	Low	High	21 & 22	High	Low	High
7 & 8	High	Low	Low	23 & 24	High	Low	Low
9 & 10	Low	High	High	25 & 26	Low	High	High
11 & 12	Low	High	Low	27 & 28	Low	High	Low
13 & 14	Low	Low	High	29 & 30	Low	Low	High
15 & 16	Low	Low	Low	31 & 32	Low	Low	Low

Table 2. RTM process parameters which were used in the investigation (associated with Table 1). Pressures are absolute, i.e pressure above absolute vacuum.

	Resin A laminates		Resin B laminates	
	High	Low	High	Low
Injection pressure [bar]	2.0	not used	4.0	2.0
Vacuum pressure [bar]	0.005	0.2	0.005	not used
Mold temperature [°C]	140	120	70	60
Cure regime [°C / minutes]	180 / 35	160 / 75	120 / 20	90 / 40

Fig. 1. Thickness variation of the resin A laminates. The origin of the x axis is in the plate center.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The specimens were first cut from the plates using a band saw with a diamond blade. In order to achieve accurate dimensions and high quality edges, a diamond saw mounted in a milling machine was used for the final cutting. All specimens were dried in 60° C, 6 % relative humidity during 48 hours. Preconditioning in hot and wet conditions was made for 1000 hours at 70° C, RH 85 %. The preconditioned specimens were tested at 80° C, room humidity. In the following the abbreviation RT refers to room temperature tests, and HW to testing of environmentally exposed specimens in elevated temperature. The specimen thickness and width were measured at three locations along the specimen length (top, middle, bottom). To provide for statistical averages, five specimens were tested in each condition. All tests were performed in an INSTRON 4045 TTDM universal testing machine.

TENSILE PROPERTIES

Two types of tensile tests were performed, one ordinary tensile test (T) mainly according to the ASTM 3039-93 standard [1], and one notched tensile test according to the CRAG 303 standard for Open Hole Tensile (OHT) tests [2]. Tests were performed both at room temperature on dry specimens, and at elevated temperature on specimens which had been preconditioned in hot/wet environment. The test results are summarized in Table 3, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

TENSILE TESTS (T)

Since un-notched tensile properties are relatively little affected by the matrix, no big difference was expected between specimens made with different process parameters. The specimens were 25 mm wide and 300 mm long and had adhesively bonded tabs. Different tab configurations were tested ranging from glass fiber/polyester to aluminum, both straight and tapered. The best results were obtained with 4 mm thick non tapered 0°/90° woven glass/epoxy tabs glued with Araldite 1414. A constant crosshead speed of 4 mm/min was used which resulted in failure in approximately 1.5 minutes. Initially two 50 mm clip gauges were used to detect specimen bending due to misalignment. However, the bending proved negligible and in the remaining tests only one clip gauge was used. Initially some clip gauge slipping was observed. Water soluble white ink was applied on the specimen surface to increase friction and this proved to work satisfactorily.

The tensile failure *strain* was throughout the investigation relatively constant, $\epsilon_c = 1.42$ % (with a coefficient of variation (CV) of 4.6 %). No significant change in failure strain could be observed for different matrices or fiber fractions. A trend however can be seen in laminates nos. 20, 24 and 28. All these were resin B laminates with low cure conditions and they all show a drop in maximum strain in HW conditions. Considering the scatter this drop is not really significant but interesting to note since, as shown below, the strength was also affected.

In room temperature the average failure *force* of the resin B specimens was 5 % higher than for resin A specimens. However, in HW conditions there was no difference. For all the resin A laminates, except no. 12, the failure forces were a few percent higher in HW than in RT conditions. Note that these trends were too small to be considered significant. The influence of the thickness variation was not significant other than for the two thinnest laminates (14 & 16, $v_f = 60$ %). These laminates were significantly thinner than the average and proved to carry approximately 5 % lower force than the average in RT condition. The laminates 20, 24 and 28 have a severe drop in failure loads in HW compared with RT condition. The general insensitivity of failure load to environmental conditions and RTM process parameters is not regarded as surprising since the failure load is mainly fiber dependent.

The failure stress was calculated as the failure force divided by the specimens smallest cross section area. The failure stresses proved to be higher for the resin A laminates, which in this investigation were thinner but had the same amount of fibers as the resin B laminates. The generally lower failure stresses of the resin B laminates are thus not believed to depend on differences in the resin but the cross section area. The low performance in maximum forces for laminates 14 and 16 was compensated by small cross section area and the stress is well in level with the average.

The elastic moduli were calculated by a least squares fit of sampled points in the region between 0.1 % and 0.6 % strain. The mid cross section area was used. Not surprising, the moduli are closely related to the individual cross section areas. Consequently laminates 14 & 16 have the

highest moduli. To eliminate the influence of thickness variations a more representative measure, E^* , was introduced. E^* is the modulus multiplied by the corresponding specimen thickness. This new entity showed an increase for all the resin A laminates in HW conditions compared with RT. The increase, 1.3 % in average, was well within the standard deviation and may thus be insignificant, but still it was present for all of the 8 laminates. For resin B no consistent difference could be seen between RT and HW.

OPEN HOLE TENSILE TESTS (OHT)

The tensile notch sensitivity specimen was 40 mm wide with a 6.0 mm drilled hole in the center. Great effort was put into centering the hole accurately. The stresses discussed below are based on gross cross section area. Tabs proved unnecessary. The test machine crosshead speed was kept constant at 6 mm/min which lead to failure in about 1 minute.

The resin A laminates showed a quite consistent drop in failure *force* of about 5 % in HW. This was not the case for the resin B laminates where for some laminates the force even increased slightly in HW. At RT the failure load was approximately 8 % lower for the resin B laminates than for the resin A laminates. Generally, the failure load seemed not to be related to the specimen thickness, and the better performance of the resin A laminates are supposedly matrix related.

The notched tensile *stresses* in essence mirrors the laminate thicknesses. The resin A laminates show a consistently lower performance in HW than in RT, which though does not apply for the resin B laminates. The failure stress of resin A is approximately 15 % higher than for resin B.

OPEN HOLE COMPRESSION TESTS (OHC)

The compression notch sensitivity test was performed, according to the CRAG 402 standard [2], on the same type of specimens as in the OHT tests, i.e. 40 mm wide with a 6.0 mm drilled hole. The stresses were again based on gross cross section area. The test machine crosshead speed was kept constant at 3 mm/min. An anti-buckling guide in accordance with the standard was used. The test results are summarized in Table 3, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. The failure *forces* demonstrate a significant drop in HW conditions for both matrices. Considering the failure forces, resin A was 6 % stronger in RT and 13 % in HW compared with resin B.

The substantial HW degradation in failure force was present also in failure stresses. Since the resin A laminates were thinner than the resin B laminates, the failure stresses of resin A dominate over resin B even more (15 % in RT and 20 % in HW).

The HW degradation in failure force was very significant, 20 % for resin A and 28 % for resin B. The degradation was most distinct for resin B. The explanation may be softening of the matrix due to elevated temperature and humidity, which lead to reduction in fiber buckling stress. No drastic difference was revealed between the laminates with different RTM process parameters.

Table 3. Summary of average tensile and compressive properties for the two matrices. Within parenthesis the coefficients of variation, CV, are given in %.

	Resin A laminates		Resin B laminates	
	RT	HW	RT	HW
Tensile Force [kN]	64.7 (5.7)	65.8 (4.6)	67.5 (3.7)	65.8 (3.6)
Tensile Stress [MPa]	919 (5.6)	928 (3.9)	883 (3.5)	860 (4.2)
Tensile Strain [%]	1.41 (5.7)	1.41 (4.3)	1.44 (4.2)	1.43 (4.2)
Modulus [GPa]	63.9 (3.7)	64.5 (3.1)	59.8 (2.6)	59.8 (3.5)
E^* [kN/mm]	180 (1.9)	182 (1.4)	183 (1.5)	183 (3.0)
OHT Force [kN]	53.4 (3.6)	50.8 (2.6)	49.7 (3.6)	49.15 (3.4)
OHT Stress [MPa]	469 (3.2)	444 (2.9)	400 (2.2)	395 (1.8)
OHT/ Γ (Stress)	0.51	0.48	0.45	0.46
OHC Force [kN]	40.2 (4.6)	33.5 (6.3)	37.8 (3.7)	29.5 (3.5)
OHC Stress [MPa]	355 (2.3)	295 (2.0)	311 (1.9)	242 (2.9)
OHC/OHT (Force)	0.75	0.66	0.76	0.60

Fig. 2. Failure forces for tensile, notched tensile and notched compression tests.

Fig. 3. Failure stresses for tensile, notched tensile and notched compression tests.

CONCLUSIONS OF TENSION AND COMPRESSION EXPERIMENTS

Concerning the overall tensile properties, there were little variations between the laminates. Environmental exposure also generally had limited effect. The failure strain was throughout the investigation relatively constant, not even affected by the HW condition. The average failure force was roughly the same for the resin A and the resin B laminates whereas the stress was lower for the resin B laminates due to the larger thickness. The resin B laminates nos. 20, 24 and 28 performed poor in both maximum force and failure stress. For the thinnest laminates, nos. 14 and 16, the failure forces were low. However when comparing the stresses, these laminates were well in level with the overall average.

For the notched tensile force however there is a degradation for the resin A laminates in HW conditions. In RT, the resin A laminates perform 7 % better in notched tensile strength than resin B laminates. The notched tensile strength is overall in essence half the un-notched strength. The environmental degradation factor is neglectable for most tensile properties except for resin A notched tensile strength where a degradation of 5.6 % is present.

The most significant difference between RT and HW conditions was revealed in notched compression, OHC. The resin A laminates lost 20 % and the resin B laminates lost 28 % in failure force.

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

Interlaminar fracture toughness experiments were performed mainly in accordance with the ESIS standard [3]. For mode I fracture toughness a double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen was used, and for the mode II fracture toughness an end notched flexure (ENF) specimen. 20 mm wide specimens were used and the crack propagation was observed through a traveling microscope. A 15 μm thick unfolded Teflon crack starter film was molded in the laminate symmetry layer. No further pre cracking was used. Water soluble white ink was applied on the specimen sides to enhance crack tip visibility. Both the mode I and mode II test results are plotted in Fig. 4.

MODE I FRACTURE TOUGHNESS (DCB)

The crack starter had a nominal length of 50 mm and the test continued until the crack had propagated another 50 mm. Adhesively bonded standard hinges were used. The test machine crosshead speed was kept constant at 2 mm/min. There are several different measures of mode I fracture toughness that can be derived from the DCB test data. One is based on the point of (initial) non-linearity in the load displacement curve (NL), one on 5 % increase of initial compliance (5 %), one on the point of the first visual crack propagation (Vis), and one on the maximum applied load (Max). No international agreement on the use of a single measure for fracture toughness seems to exist. In this investigation the objective was to compare different materials/conditions and no absolute value was of interest. Due to the observed significant increase of fracture toughness with crack growth the use of one single measure seemed unrealistic. In agreement with Hojo et.al. [4] in their studies on epoxy matrices with woven reinforcements, substantial unstable crack growth was observed. Hojo et.al. suggest that there is a inhomogeneity of the fracture toughness caused by the woven fabric.

After testing it was discovered that the Teflon starter films were sometimes quite unevenly cut prior to molding, which lead to poorly defined starter crack tips. This indicated that the NL & Vis measures could be quite unreliable. Therefore a modified initial fracture toughness measure, G_{lc}^{init} , was introduced based on the first 5 mm of crack propagation. The hypothesis was that this entity would be less sensitive to imperfections in the starter crack tip. A second entity, G_{lc}^R , was also calculated based on the average of the R curve for crack lengths larger than 60 mm. Both these fracture toughnesses, together with mode II fracture toughnesses, are plotted in Fig. 4. The average ratio between G_{lc}^{init} and G_{lc}^R was approximately 0.6 for both the resin A and the resin B laminates. However, the resin A laminates showed a larger scatter, with G_{lc}^{init} ranging from 0.44 to 0.85, than the resin B laminates, with G_{lc}^{init} ranging from 0.54 to 0.66. Having only comparison of different

laminates in mind, G_{lc}^{init} and G_{lc}^R appear to be almost equivalent. The resin A laminates showed a larger scatter than the resin B laminates in both measures. An interesting result was the good performance of resin A in terms of G_{lc}^R for laminates nos. 3, 7, 9 and 15. Regarding G_{lc}^{init} these laminates did however not stand out. No common factor in manufacturing parameters or v_f could be found for these laminates.

MODE II FRACTURE TOUGHNESS (ENF)

Each experiment was preceded by an experimental compliance calibration in the elastic range according to [3]. The nominal starter crack tip was then placed in the middle between the center and the outer loading point. Tanaka et.al. [5] suggest interesting methods for stabilization of the crack growth by different techniques. They also state that, as for mode I, a single point in the load deflection curve is not enough to characterize the material. The suggested methods for achieving stable crack growth were not used in this investigation, but the test machine crosshead speed was kept constant at 1 mm/min. As for mode I there are several possible measures of mode II fracture toughness that can be extracted. The point of first, through the microscope, observed crack propagation was recorded but was regarded as unreliable due to the same reason as for mode I, i.e. unevenly cut Teflon starter film. Two measures based on the point of the non-linearity (NL) and on the maximum load (Max), respectively, were calculated. Both of these values used the experimental compliance calibration. To achieve a consistent and less subjective definition of the NL point a software was developed which evaluated the tests by using the Instron result files as input. The results of the testing are presented in Fig. 4. Laminate no. 3 showed a mysteriously large scatter. Fracture toughnesses using the NL and Max evaluation techniques were satisfactorily correlated. The average energy release rate based on the point of non-linearity was for resin A laminates 1.27 kJ/m² and for resin B laminates 1.29 kJ/m². The average energy release rate based on the maximum load was 10-15 % higher than the NL values, 1.48 kJ/m² for resin A and 1.43 kJ/m² for resin B. There was no significant difference in mode II fracture toughness between the resin A and the resin B laminates.

Fig. 4. Mode I & II fracture toughness results.

CONCLUSIONS FROM THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS EXPERIMENTS

For both the mode I and mode II fracture toughness experiments, two measures respectively were extracted to represent the materials. One value represented the energy release rate in the initial phase where fiber bridging was expected to be minor. The interpretation of the initial value was difficult due to blunt initial crack tips, in front of which there were resin rich regions. Further, the Teflon starter films were sometimes wavy, curled or skew. The fracture toughnesses extracted from points after the initial phase were likely to be strongly influenced by fiber bridging, which was also observed through the microscope. In the case of mode II another phenomenon also affected the results: the crack followed a wavy path along the woven reinforcement and the geometric structure of the crack surfaces is likely to have restrained crack shear displacements. There was no significant difference in mode II toughness between the laminates of the two investigated matrices. The resin A laminates however had a larger scatter than the resin B laminates. Regarding the influence of process parameters the resin B seemed quite insensitive. The resin A laminates nos. 3, 7, 9 and 15 had a substantially higher mode I toughness than the rest of the laminates with the same resin. The corresponding difference was not present in mode II. No common factor was found for these laminates regarding molding conditions or fiber volume fractions.

DISCUSSION

Laminates of two different matrix materials and the same reinforcement were RTM manufactured under a number of different manufacturing conditions. Standard tests were then performed in both room temperature, and elevated temperature and moisture. As a general conclusion, the mechanical properties of these two material systems was not significantly affected by the different process parameters. Differing environmental conditioning and specimen thicknesses had a larger influence. Open hole compression strength was the entity which was most degraded by the hot and wet conditioning.

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